

Rocks from the ice: DEMs of subglacial concretions through photogrammetry

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Abstract— At the ice-rock interface of glaciers developing on carbonate bedrocks, carbonate deposits known as “subglacial concretions” can form. These deposits are usually found on the lee side of obstacles and are the results of melting of the basal ice at the stoss side of the same obstacles and subsequent regelation at the lee side. Although their potential as palaeoenvironmental proxies is still not clear, it has been demonstrated that these deposits can provide information about past glacier dynamics. However, their fragility prevents their conservation over long periods of time, and they can be destroyed by erosion and weathering processes within approximately 50 years since their exposure. Considering the fast glacier retreat we are experiencing, it is important to document and study subglacial concretions before they are forever gone. Subglacial concretions documentation was carried out producing DEMs with sub-millimetric resolution through photogrammetry. These models allow the morphometric analyses of subglacial carbonate deposits and represent an important tool to understand their formation and provide a solid base for investigating the relation between the development of specific micro landforms and glacier dynamics. Subglacial concretions are generally located in not easily accessible sites, which can present extreme environmental conditions, we thus tested an affordable and efficient way to produce reliable data in these environments. In this work we investigate three sites in the Dolomites (NE Italy), exploring the use of photogrammetry in providing high resolution DEMs of subglacial concretions to support their morphometric analyses.

I. INTRODUCTION

Global warming is causing rapid continental glacier retreat worldwide. The Alpine area appears to be one of the most affected

regions with an annual glacier mass loss of about 1.2 kg/m^2 between 1997 and 2017 (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)/WGMS). LiDAR and both aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry technologies are widely used to measure changes in glacier mass balance and monitor glacier evolution [1][2]. These methods can provide important data on a large scale but can also be useful to document morphologies related to glacier evolution at a smaller scale.

Indeed, at the ice rock interface several processes occur which can lead to the development of specific morphologies and to the deposition of carbonate crusts which are generally defined as “subglacial concretions”, where carbonate bedrocks are present. These deposits have been first observed and described in the early '70s in the Canadian Rocky Mountains [3] and consist in carbonate crusts deposited on the lee side of obstacles. Their formation has been related to melting and re-gelation processes of thin films of water at the base of glaciers [3][4][5][6][7].

Subglacial concretions potential as paleoenvironmental proxies is not clear since their isotopic signals ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) can be affected by strong kinetic fractionation [8][9]. Lipar et al. (2021) [10] dated back to the Younger Dryas and the LGM some subglacial concretions from the Triglav Glacier (Slovenia), showing their potential in providing information about glaciers development during the current interglacial phase. Indeed, once exposed to weathering, these subglacial deposits soon disappear: Frisia and Borsato (1994) [11] estimated a maximum duration of subglacial concretions of about 50 years in the “Dolomiti di Brenta” area. This suggests that subglacial carbonate deposits, when found, indicate the absence of an icecap for a maximum of about 50 years. If we consider the widespread presence of

Figure 1. Sites where subglacial concretions were documented. a) Tuckett glacier; b) Marmolada glacier; c) Antelao glacier. In a) it is possible to observe evident erosion/corrosion morphologies. In b) and c) fluted carbonate crusts are elongated according to the direction of the ice flow.

carbonate bedrock in the central and eastern part of the Italian Alps and the massive glacier retreat this region is experiencing, it comes out that new subglacial concretions are being exposing rapidly. But they will not last for long. It is thus important to document and study them before they are destroyed by weathering and erosion processes. For this purpose, it is useful to investigate methods which can be easily performed in extreme environments, and which can be affordable for the documentation of these ephemeral witnesses of past glaciers, such as photogrammetric techniques, which are widely used to document archaeological findings.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

A. The surveyed area

The prevalent rock type in the Dolomites is represented by carbonates. In this area the glacier coverage is disappearing fast. Indeed, of the 33 glaciers documented in the late 1950's, only 9 are still active [12]. Considering this massive retreat and the type of bedrock characterizing this region, in several areas subglacial concretions have been recently exposed and are prone to their rapid disappearance. In this study we considered three of the most representative sites of the Dolomites, surveyed in 2020 and 2021: Marmolada, Antelao and Tuckett glaciers (Fig.1). Marmolada

massif hosts the largest glacier of the Dolomites which currently represents the 55 % of the total glacier area of this region, and that has lost 65.7 % of its volume since the 1980s [12]. On the freshly exposed areas at the glacier front it is possible to observe abundant subglacial concretions characterized by carbonate crusts and deposits elongated in the same direction of the ice flow (Fig.1). Similar deposits can be observed on bedrock and boulder surfaces recently exposed by the Antelao glacier retreat (Fig.1). Less developed subglacial concretions associated with marked erosion/corrosion morphologies partly due to subglacial karst processes have been instead observed at the flanks of the area recently occupied by Tuckett glacier (Fig.1).

B. Photogrammetric survey

Eight boulders in Marmolada massif, five in Antelao and ten in Tuckett site were chosen for photogrammetric documentation. Their dimension ranges between 2.12 and 47.6 m² in the first site, 0.76 and 6.17 m² in the second, and between 0.2 and 3.26 m² in the latter.

A total of 1257, 1878 and 1559 photos were taken in the three sites, respectively. These photographs were taken using the SLR camera NIKON D810 with a focal length of 35, 24 and 50 mm in the Marmolada site, the full frame mirrorless camera SONY

Figure 2. On the left the orthomosaic of the surface of a surveyed boulder from Antelao glacier. The white square indicates a subglacial concretion. In the center a closeup on the DEM in correspondence of the subglacial concretion. On the right a profile of the subglacial concretion realized with the profile tool in QGIS.

ILCE-7RM3 with a focal length of 47 mm in Antelao site, and the RICOH GR III camera with a focal length of 18 mm. All photos were taken manually, without the help of a tripod. For each documented boulder, at least two metersticks have been placed as a reference. The calculation of 3D models of all the surveyed boulders has been performed using the Agisoft Metashape software. Each model has been scaled using the references placed during the fieldwork reaching a scale bar error between 0.01 and 0.4 mm. The ground resolution of the calculated models ranges between 0.074 and 0.194 mm/pixel with a reprojection error between 0.33 and 0.766 pixels for the Marmolada site, between 0.0491 and 0.104 mm/pixel with a reprojection error between 0.745 and 1.58 mm pixels in the Antelao site, and between 0.0425 and 0.106 mm/pixel with a reprojection error between 0.572 and 1.3 pixels in Tuckett site. From each point cloud a digital elevation model and an orthomosaic have been calculated to be used in a GIS environment. The models of the boulders presenting the most representative subglacial concretions and erosion morphologies have been analysed using the QGIS 3.22.4 software (Fig.2). These models allowed to highlight and measure the morphologies of these concretions, which are mainly formed of crusts and ribbon shaped deposits with crests and furrows elongated in the same direction of the ice flow, sometimes ending with stalactite-shape protrusions, and to analyze the pattern and distribution of the erosion/corrosion morphologies. Using this procedure it has thus been possible to investigate glacial micro-

landforms at the sub-millimetric scale, leading to the identification of at least four different types of subglacial concretions according to their morphometric characteristics, mainly consisting in differences in crest length, surface roughness, crest width, and furrow depth. Petrographic and geochemical analyses will be carried out to investigate the eventual presence of specific patterns characterizing the identified subglacial concretion types. The distribution of each subglacial concretion type with respect to the past glacier flow will be also examined, thus investigating the potential of morphometric analyses in the identification of subglacial deposits which may provide further information about past glacier dynamics. This work confirms photogrammetry as an efficient and affordable method for the production of high-quality models for the description of small-scale morphologies in extreme environments.

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